

ACRIDINES AS ANTISEPTICS. PART II

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Various sulphonamides have been reacted with 5-aminoacridine to form 'onium' salts and their bacteriostatic properties have been compared with 5-aminoacridine and the respective sulphonamide.

Recently sulphonamide compounds are being used as local antiseptics but it is generally noticed that minute amounts of *p*-aminobenzoic acid antagonise the antibacterial effects of sulphanilamide derivatives containing a free '*p*-amino' grouping. Of course, compounds are now known which are not affected by the presence of *p*-amino grouping in the sulphanilamide molecule (*cf.* Goetchius and Lawrence, *J. Bact.*, 1945, 49, 575). An idea is gaining ground that the above antagonism is due to the interference with some metabolic function of bacterial cell. Mudd (*J. Bact.*, 1945, 49, 527) further suggests that sulphanilamide has affinity for respiratory enzyme protein and as such compounds like sulphapyridine, sulphathiazole, sulphadiazine, containing groups as present in co-enzyme complex, exert a more enhanced antibacterial activity. On this hypothesis, incorporation of any other component known to inhibit the respiratory enzymes of the bacterial cells might increase the antibacterial effect of a sulphanilamide derivative. Recently, Haas (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1944, 155, 315, 321) has noticed the inhibitory action of 'atebrin' on the respiratory enzyme. 'Atebrin' is a 5-aminoacridine derivative and the 5-aminoacridines have again been noticed to exert pronounced bactericidal action (Rubbo, Albert and Maxwell, *Brit. J. Expt. Path.*, 1942, 23, 69; *cf.* Das-Gupta and Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 364). Accordingly it was considered to be of interest to study the influence of this 5-aminoacridine on some simpler and well known sulphanilamides like *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide, sulphanilacetamide, sulphanilylbenzamide, sulphapyridine and sulphathiazole. As the latter compounds are somewhat acidic in nature, it was expected that they would react readily with 5-aminoacridine and the resulting compounds might be easily compared with the parent sulphanilamides as well as with mixtures containing molar amounts of the different components.

The different salts of the general formula (III) obtained by the interaction of the sulphanilamides of the form (I) with 5-aminoacridine (II) are not equally stable. The sulphabenzamide, the sulphacetamide and sulphathiazole compounds, obtained by reacting in a hydrated solvent (alcohol), can be easily crystallised out from the same solvent. The interaction between sulphapyridine and 5-aminoacridine may be better carried out in a non-hydrated solvent, but the 'onium' compounds easily break up into the constituent parts. This is quite in keeping with the acidic properties of the different sulpha compounds as is evident from their acid dissociation constants as found in this laboratory.

The various onium compounds, equimolecular mixtures of 5-aminoacridine and the different sulphanilamides, 5-aminoacridine itself and the individual sulphanilamide derivative were incubated at 37° for 72 hours in a medium made from papain digest-glucose-phosphate meat broth containing about 500 organisms per 5 c.c. of broth. The table below shows the minimal inhibiting concentration expressed in milligrams of the antiseptic (drug) per 100 c.c. of broth. From the table it would be noticed that the antibacterial activity of the sulphanilamide derivatives (column under *a*) is considerably enhanced by incorporation of 5-aminoacridine whether in the form of their onium salt (column *c*) or in the form of equimolecular mixture (column *b*). In inhibiting the growth of *strepto haemolyticus* as well as that of *staph.aureus*, the two common pathogenic organisms met with in common wounds and abrasions, a synergistic action is noticed whenever a sulpha drug is mixed with 5-aminoacridine. As these antiseptics might be useful in the treatment of various types of wounds and abrasions, work is in progress to prepare certain ointments in suitable water-washable bases incorporating these compounds for study of their antibacterial activities by the well known cup agar plate method.

TABLE I

Antibacterial activity in vitro

Minimal inhibiting concentration in mg. of drug per 100 c.c. of culture medium at 37.5° for 72 hours.

Organism.	5-Amino-acridine.	Sulphathiazole			Sulphanilyl benzamide.			Sulphanilyl acetamide.			Sulphapyridine.			Sulphanilamide.	
		<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>
<i>Bact. Coli</i>	2	1	1	1	5	5	5	10	5	2	1	5	5	100	2
<i>Strep. haemolyt</i>	1	15	0.5	0.2	..	1	0.5	1	0.5	..	1	0.5	0.5
<i>Staph. Aureus</i>	2	>10	1	1	>20	5	4	>50	4	2	10	4	4	>50	1
<i>Bact. Proteus</i>	2	2	2	2	..	4	10	..	4	4	..	4	4	..	4
<i>B. pyocyanea</i>	10	50	20	50	..	20	50	..	20	50	..	50	50	..	50
<i>Bact. Dysent</i>	..	0.4	1	0.5	10	2	2	20	1	1	2	2	2	..	1
<i>Fleuzner (y)</i>	0.4	0.2	..	0.5	0.5	..	2	2	1	0.5	0.5	..	0.2
<i>V. Cholerae (Inaba)</i>	..	0.1	1	1	..	2	1	..	2	1	..	1	1	..	1
<i>Pnemo, Type I</i>	1	0.2	..	4	2	..	2	1	..	4	2
<i>Enterococcus</i>	..	>5	1	1	>100	2	2	>50	2	2	5	2	2	>100	1

a—Sulphanilamide derivative alone

b—Mixture of the sulphanilamide derivative and 5-aminoacridine.

c—Compound formed by the sulphanilamide derivative with 5-aminoacridine.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-Aminoacridonium sulphathiazole.—To a solution of 5-aminoacridine (1 g.) in 95% spirit, was added sulphathiazole (1.3 g.) and the mixture refluxed till complete solution. On cooling, shining yellow crystals of 5-aminoacridonium sulphathiazole, m.p. 218° (decomp.), were obtained. (Found : N, 14.99. $C_{22}H_{19}O_2N_3S_2$ requires N, 15.59 per cent).

5-Aminoacridonium sulphacetamide.—Similarly 5-aminoacridine (1 g.) dissolved in 95% spirit was refluxed with *p*-aminobenzene sulphacetamide (1.1 g.) for about 10 minutes when shining yellow crystals of 5-aminoacridonium sulphacetamide were obtained. Solids collected after cooling were purified by recrystallisation from spirit, m.p. 258° (decomp.). (Found : N, 13.86. $C_{21}H_{20}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 13.72 per cent).

5-Aminoacridonium sulphabenzamide.—To a clear solution of 5-aminoacridine (1 g.) in alcohol was added a clear solution of *p*-aminobenzene sulphabenzamide (1.4 g.) in alcohol and shaken thoroughly well. After about half an hour, shining yellow crystals of 5-aminoacridonium sulphabenzamide began to appear. These were filtered and washed well with alcohol when crystals, m.p. 226°, were obtained. (Found: N, 11.6. $C_{26}H_{22}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 11.9 per cent).

5-Aminoacridonium sulphapyridine.—To a solution of 5-aminoacridine (1 g.) in acetone was added a solution of 2-sulphanilylpyridine (1.2 g.) in acetone. The acetone solution was concentrated at room temperature in partial *vacuo*, then diluted with water when shining light yellow needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 131°, were obtained. (Found: N, 13.9; H_2O , 11.3. $C_{24}H_{21}O_2N_5S$, $3H_2O$ requires N, 14.08; H_2O , 10.8 per cent).

5-Aminoacridonium sulphanilamide.—To 5-aminoacridine (1 g.) dissolved in rectified spirit was added *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide (0.88 g.) dissolved in spirit and shaken thoroughly. After standing overnight, 5-aminoacridonium sulphanilamide, m.p. 222° (decomp.), was obtained on diluting with ether as shining yellow crystals. (Found: N, 10.93; H_2O , 25.5. $C_{19}H_{18}O_2N_4S$, $7H_2O$ requires N, 11.3; H_2O , 25.6 per cent).

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A SIMPLE RELATION BETWEEN VISCOSITY AND SURFACE TENSION OF LIQUIDS*

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Newton Friend's equation ($\gamma = k\sqrt{\eta}$) has been shown to apply very well to the viscosity and surface tension data on a number of unassociated liquids belonging to different families. The constant, k , agrees with the quantity (Parachor/Rheochor) within fairly close limits as expected.

In contrast to the various complicated equations connecting viscosity and surface tension of liquids (Silverman and Roseveare, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4460; Buehler, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 1207; Tripathi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 51) Newton Friend's equation (*Nature*, 1942, 150, 432; *Phil Mag.*, 1943, 34, 643) : $\gamma = k\sqrt{\eta}$ between viscosity and surface tension of unassociated liquids is one of remarkable simplicity. It contains no arbitrary constant as k is given by the quantity $(P/R)^4$; P (parachor) can be calculated from atomic and structural constants, the same possibility being indicated for R (rheochor) as well (Bhagwat, Toshniwal and Moghe, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 29). In the present paper, the relation has been shown to apply very well to a number of unassociated liquids over wide ranges of temperature (Table I). Except for a few erratic cases, invariably at the lowest or highest temperatures, the equation fits in with data on most substances within 2 to 3%.

* This work was done in the Chemical Laboratory, Science College, Patna.